

Search for additional Higgs in the 2HDM model at Future Lepton Colliders using Boosted Decision Trees and Anomaly Detection Techniques

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Abstract

This article explores the application of Boosted Decision Trees and Anomaly Detection Techniques to search for additional Higgs in the Higgs Doublet model at Future Lepton colliders. The results in the article uses a set of open-source programs that may be used to work with the Future Circular colliders Software and Key4Hep generated data to search for additional Higgs via Anomaly Detection Techniques in the l^+l^-jj final states. The code developed for this paper is available from https://github.com/amanmdesai/AnomalyDetection_lepton_collider.

1 Introduction

The discovery of Higgs Boson with a mass of 125 GeV by the ATLAS and CMS collaborations was useful in corroborating the Standard Model (SM) of particle physics [1, 2]. However, several important physics questions still remain unanswered within the SM. The searches for additional Higgs in the context of Higgs Doublet Model (2HDM) [3] is well motivated and extends the SM by including two Higgs doublet instead of one. Owing to the addition of second Higgs doublet as well as the spontaneous symmetry breakdown, it leads to eight scalar particle states. Out of these eight scalar states, three are absorbed by gauge bosons (W^\pm , Z) to give them masses, whereas the other five are physical bosons- h , H^0 , A , H^+ , H^- .

The local excesses at the mass of 96 GeV were observed in $e^+e^- \rightarrow Z(H \rightarrow b\bar{b})$ searches with respect to the Standard Model by the LEP [4] and CMS [5] of ($\sim 3\sigma$) at around 96 GeV (98 GeV) particle mass. Such signals could be explained, for example, by models such as the 2HDM [5] or 2HDM with an additional scalar [6].

The Future Circular Collider (FCCee) should, in principle, be able to search for this scalar particle with a mass around 96 GeV. In this article, we use machine learning techniques such as the Boosted Decision Trees (BDT) and Anomaly Detection Techniques (ADT) to search for this new predicted scalar particle at a mass of 96 GeV.

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2 Simulated Samples

The background and signal processes used in this study were first simulated with Madgraph [7], which evaluated the cross sections and then these were passed on to Pythia8 [8] and Delphes [9] (as provided by Key4HEP) for parton shower and detector simulation, respectively. The background included all SM processes that result in 2 jet + 2 oppositely charged leptons. For the moment we have used Higgs effective field theory model to include contributions from Higgs. The signal was simulated using the 2HDM model as provided with Madgraph with the following Madgraph syntax: `generate e+ e- > z h1, z > l+ l-, h1 > j j` where h1 represents the light Higgs of the 2HDM model. The mass of the h1 particle was set at 96 GeV. Therefore, the final sample also includes the IDEA detector response for the Monte Carlo processes. Some motivation regarding application of Anomaly Detection to search for new physics were adopted from [10].

3 Softwares

The softwares were called via a combination of Docker [11] and CVMFS framework [12]. The docker image used in this study is provided by the AIDASOFT collaboration via their github webpage¹. The MadGraph5 and Pythia8 softwares were used for Monte Carlo Simulation of background and signal processes. Delphes, as implemented in FCC Software, was used for simulation. The above softwares were operated via their interfaces to FCC software/Key4HEP framework. FCCAnalyses software was used for the initial analysis [13] of data, which was in the EDM4HEP format[14]. For Machine Learning purposes we converted the ROOT files into Pandas .csv files via Uproot[15]. Scikit-learn software was used for preprocessing and the following Machine Learning softwares were used for training and inferences: Tensorflow [16], ROOT-TMVA [17] and XGBoost [18]. Matplotlib [19], ROOT [20],and FCCAnalyses were used for plotting.

4 Input Variables

We make use of low level features- such as the four-momenta of first two jets, muons, and electrons. As a result, we have 24 variables as features fed to the Machine Learning model owing to motivation from the paper [21]. Figure 1 gives the distribution of input variables that were used for Machine Learning². Before giving samples to the model, they were normalized.

5 Machine Learning Method

We have used the BDT method provided via TMVA. The following are the parameters of the BDT:- Maximum depth: 7, number of trees: 200, minimum nodesize 1%, Boosttype: Grad, and separation index: Gini. The BDT output and the Receiver Operating Characteristics [ROC]

¹<https://github.com/orgs/AIDAsoft/packages>.

²The issue with variable ϕ has been updated (see e.g., <https://github.com/HEP-FCC/FCCAnalyses/pull/237>).

Figure 1: Input variables.

Figure 2

curve for BDT as obtained from TMVA are shown in Figure 2. We see that the area under the curve for the BDT ROC is 0.93.

We have also used the Anomaly Detection Techniques (ADT). The model is trained on a background sample (SM). The goal of this training is to reduce the loss for SM processes. When one feeds a BSM signal, it is likely to be assigned higher loss, which leads to its discrimination from SM. The ADT network consists of 7 layers. The first three layers have 32, 24 and 16 nodes, whereas the last three layers have 16, 24, 32 nodes. The central layer (4th layer) has 5 nodes. We have used Adam [22] for optimizing the learning rates. The following parameters were used for Adam: learning rate is set to 0.08, beta_1 is 0.42, beta_2 is 0.32, epsilon is $1e - 03$, and amsgrad is set to True. Note that we have used 200 Epochs and a batch size of 512. The framework of analysis is to some extent motivated from ADC2021 challenge[10].

The training and validation loss and accuracy for a given epoch is given in Figure 3. This plot indicates that the training leads to the lower losses and higher accuracy with the epochs. The mean square error is given in Figure 4. This plot shows that the mean square error is more likely less for background sample as compared to the signal, which has tails in the higher mean square error region. The ROC curve for anomaly detection technique is shown in Figure 5. The grey strips represent the performance of a random model. The area under the curve for ROC is 0.88, which is better than a random classifier/model.

The Machine Learning models presented here have not undergone the step of hyperparameter optimization.

6 Outlook

We have used the ADT for FCCee and see that these techniques would be helpful in distinguishing the 2HDM BSM signal from the SM background. We have also made use of the BDT method to separate the signal from the background. The possible next steps in this study would be to have

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Training Loss and Accuracy

Figure 4: Mean Squared Error Loss.

Figure 5: Receiver Operating Curve.

a proper background modelling as well to have a hyperparameter optimized machine learning methods.

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